

**ADVANCES IN MODIFICATION OF ADOMIAN DECOMPOSITION METHOD
AND THEIR APPLICATION TO INTEGRAL EQUATIONS**

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Abstract

This study presents a new modified Adomian decomposition approach for solving Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential equations. The suggested approach attempts to improve the efficiency and accuracy of the present method for dealing with this class of equations. The modified Adomian decomposition approach was shown to be useful in generating trustworthy solutions for a wide variety of Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential equations. Our discoveries help to enhance numerical methods for solving integro-differential equations, which have applications in a variety of scientific and engineering areas.

Keywords: Adomian Decomposition Method, Taylor Series, Volterra-Fredholm Integro-differential equations, Adomian polynomial.

Introduction

It is critical to recognize the importance of tackling complicated mathematical issues in many scientific and engineering disciplines while presenting integro-differential equations with the newly modified Adomian decomposition approach. This approach entails breaking down the answer into a sequence of terms and solving for each term iteratively.

According to Uwaheren *et al.* (2022), the Akbari-Ganji Method (AGM) is effective for unknown coefficients since it applies boundary conditions to consecutive derivatives and integrals of the problem to generate a system of equations. Mamun-Ur-Rashid and Goutan (2019) explained how the well-known Homotopy Perturbation Method (HPM) is utilized to discover approximate solutions to the nonlinear Liernard Differential Equation (LDE) with various boundary conditions. However, the solution's HPM nature appears to be complete.

Oyedepo *et al.* (2019) revealed how to solve fractional integro-differential equations (FIDE) using the homotopy perturbation method, resulting in a system of linear algebraic equations. Olayiwola *et al.* (2008) investigated the results of employing an integral order differential equation and an Adomian decomposition technique to solve a fractional order differential equation of order greater than 1. The Adomian decomposition approach has been proven to be reliable and efficient. Abubakar & Taiwo (2014) used the usual integral collocation Approximation Method to develop numerical solutions to specific higher orders linear Fredholm-Volterra Integro-Differential Equations.

According to Abdulla-Al-Mamun *et al.* (2019), the VIM is utilized to solve a vast class of nonlinear problems with approximations that converge swiftly to precise solutions. It is worth noting that the Lagrange multiplier minimizes the number of iterations on the integral operator. Li and Pang (2020) presented a method for quantitatively assessing approximate solutions obtained by the decomposition method using fractional derivatives. Verma and Karma (2008) used the Lane-Emden type equation to demonstrate how the ultimate purpose of any scientific endeavour is to improve well-being and human health. Uwaheren *et al.* (2020), the assumed approximation solution is subtracted from a slightly perturbed form of the general class, and the resultant equation is collocated at evenly spaced interior locations to produce a system of linear algebraic equations. Adebisi *et al.* (2021) discussed Galerkin's Method (GM) which was used to solve Volterra integro-differential equations using the Chebyshev polynomial basis function, demonstrating the method's efficacy.

Mustafa and Yakin (2012) described the Chebyshev collocation method, which transforms a mixed linear integro delay differential-difference equation and the given conditions into a matrix equation that corresponds to a system of linear algebraic equations. The relationships between self-efficacy, work engagement, and job satisfaction were also investigated using correlation and regression analyses. Taiwo and Ishola (2009) explored how the differential sections of the equation are employed to generate canonical polynomials, whereas the nonlinear situations are linearization schemes of order, resulting in repetition.

Method of Solution

Several ADM modifications have recently been developed and applied to integral equations. However, these approaches have several limitations. The investigation of the modified Adomian decomposition technique comprises a full description and assessment of several iterations, including the numerical parts, by contrasting two different approaches to measure their applicability to diverse scenarios. We will base our assumption on the decomposition of the source term in the Taylor series of the form

$$h(s) = \sum_{j=0}^{+\infty} h_j(s) \quad (1)$$

and the new recursive relation obtained as:

$$u_0(s) = h_0(s), \quad (2)$$

$$u_1(s) = h_1(s) + h_2(s) + \lambda \int_a^x k(s,t)(L(u_0(s)) + A_0)dt, \quad (3)$$

$$u_2(s) = h_3(s) + h_4(s) + \lambda \int_a^x k(s,t)(L(u_1(s)) + A_1)dt, \quad (4)$$

⋮

$$u_{j+1}(s) = h_{2(j+1)}(s) + h_{2(j+1)-1}(s) + \lambda \int_a^x k(s, t)(L(u_j(s)) + A_j)dt. \tag{5}$$

And subsequently the function $u(s)$ is obtained as

$$u(s) = \sum_{j=0}^{+\infty} u_j(s). \tag{6}$$

Assuming that the nonlinear function is $F(u(s))$ therefore, below are few of the Adomian polynomials.

$$A_0 = F(u_0), \tag{7}$$

$$A_1 = u_1 F'(u_0), \tag{8}$$

$$A_2 = u_2 F'(u_0) + \frac{1}{2!} u_1^2 F''(u_0) \tag{9}$$

$$A_3 = u_3 F'(u_0) + u_1 u_2 F''(u_0) + \frac{1}{3!} u_1^3 F'''(u_0), \tag{10}$$

$$A_4 = u_4 F'(u_0) + \left(\frac{1}{2!} u_2^2 + u_1 u_3\right) F''(u_0) + \frac{1}{2!} u_1^2 u_2 F'''(u_0) + \frac{1}{4} u_1^4 F^{(iv)}(u_0). \tag{11}$$

Two important observations can be made here. First, A_0 depends only on u_0 , A_1 depends only on u_0 and u_1 , A_2 depends on u_0, u_1 and u_2 , and so on. Secondly, substituting these A_j 's gives:

$$\begin{aligned} F(u) &= A_0 + A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + \dots \\ &= F(u_0) + (u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + \dots)F'(u_0) + \frac{1}{2!}(u_1^2 + 2u_1u_2 + 2u_1u_3 + u_2^2)F''(u_0) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{3!}(u_1^3 + 3u_1^2u_3 + 6u_1u_2u_3 + \dots)F'''(u_0) + \dots \\ &= F(u_0) + (u - u_0)F'(u_0) + \frac{1}{2!}(u - u_0)^2F''(u_0) + \dots \end{aligned}$$

The method of equations (1) – (11) represents the New Modified Adomian Decomposition Method (NMADM). Subsequently, we shall illustrate the effectiveness of this method using some integral equations as presented in next session.

Numerical Examples

This section offers several numerical examples that were utilized in the new approach's experimentation. They were solved first using the normal ADM and then with the novel technique.

Example 1

$$u''(s) = 5s + 12s^2 - \frac{s^5}{20} - \frac{s^6}{30} + \int_0^s (s-t)u(s)dt \tag{12}$$

Subject to $u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 1$. with exact solution $u(s) = s^4 + s^3 + \sin(s)$.

By using New Modified Adomian Decomposition Method (NMADM)

Transformation of each term;

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s u''(s) ds ds = u(s) - s$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s 5s ds ds = \frac{5}{6} s^3$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s 12s^2 ds ds = s^4$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s \frac{s^5}{20} ds ds = \frac{1}{840} s^7$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s \frac{s^6}{30} ds ds = \frac{1}{1680} s^8$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s (s-t)u(t) dt ds ds$$

Substitute each term into (12)

We have

$$u(s) - s = \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4 - \frac{1}{180} s^7 - \frac{1}{1680} s^8 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s (s-t)u(t) dt ds ds$$

$$u(s) = s + \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4 - \frac{1}{180} s^7 - \frac{1}{1680} s^8 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s (s-t)u(t) dt ds ds$$

$$\text{Let } r = s + \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4 - \frac{1}{180} s^7 - \frac{1}{1680} s^8$$

Using Taylor series expansion (r, s, 10)

$$s + \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4 - \frac{1}{180} s^7 - \frac{1}{1680} s^8$$

While

$$a_0 = s$$

$$u_0 = t$$

$$g_0 = \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4$$

$$a_1 = g_0 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s (s-t)u_0 dt ds ds$$

$$a_1 = \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4 + \frac{1}{120} s^5$$

$$u_1 = \frac{5}{6} t^3 + t^4 + \frac{1}{120} t^5$$

$$g_1 = \frac{-1}{840} s^7 - \frac{1}{1680} s^8$$

$$a_2 = g_1 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s (s-t)u_1 dt ds ds$$

$$a_2 = \frac{-1}{5040} s^7 + \frac{1}{362880} s^9$$

$$u_2 = \frac{-1}{5040} t^7 + \frac{1}{362880} t^9$$

Then,

$$u_n(t) = u_0 + u_1 + u_2$$

$$u_n(t) = t + \frac{5}{6} t^3 + t^4 + \frac{1}{120} t^5 - \frac{1}{5040} t^7 + \frac{1}{362880} t^9 \tag{13}$$

Hence,

$$u_n(s) = s + \frac{5}{6} s^3 + s^4 + \frac{1}{120} s^5 - \frac{1}{5040} s^7 + \frac{1}{362880} s^9 \tag{14}$$

Example 2

$$u''(s) = -8 + 6s - 3s^2 + s^3 + \int_0^s u(t)dt + \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2st)u(t)dt \tag{15}$$

Subject to $u(0) = 2, u'(0) = 6$. with exact solution $u(s) = 2 + 6s - 3s^2$

By using New Modified Adomian Decomposition Method (NMADM)

Transformation of each term;

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s u''(s) ds ds = u(s) - 6s - 2$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s -8 ds ds = -4s^2$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s 6s ds ds = s^3$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s -3s^2 ds ds = -\frac{1}{4} s^4$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s s^3 ds ds = \frac{1}{20} s^5$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u(t) dt ds ds$$

$$\int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2st)u(t) dt ds ds$$

Substitute each term into (15)

We have

$$u(s) - 6s - 2 = -4s^2 + s^3 - \frac{1}{4} s^4 + \frac{1}{20} s^5 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u(t) dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2st)u(t) dt ds ds$$

$$u(s) = 2 + 6s - 4s^2 + s^3 - \frac{1}{4} s^4 + \frac{1}{20} s^5 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u(t) dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1 - 2st)u(t) dt ds ds$$

Let $r = 2 + 6s - 4s^2 + s^3 - \frac{1}{4} s^4 + \frac{1}{20} s^5$

Using Taylor series expansion (r, s, 10)

$$2 + 6s - 4s^2 + s^3 - \frac{1}{4}s^4 + \frac{1}{20}s^5$$

while

$$a_0 = 2$$

$$u_0 = 2$$

$$g_0 = 6s - 4s^2$$

$$a_1 = g_0 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u_0 dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1-2st)u_0 dt ds ds$$

$$a_1 = -2s^2 + 6s + \frac{1}{3}s^3$$

$$u_1 = -2t^2 + 6t + \frac{1}{3}t^3$$

$$g_1 = s^3 - \frac{1}{4}s^4$$

$$a_2 = g_1 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u_1 dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1-2st)u_1 dt ds ds$$

$$a_2 = -\frac{2}{3}s^2 - \frac{17}{45}s^3 - \frac{1}{30}s^5 + \frac{1}{360}s^6$$

$$u_2 = -\frac{2}{3}t^2 - \frac{17}{45}t^3 - \frac{1}{30}t^5 + \frac{1}{360}t^6$$

$$g_2 = \frac{1}{20}s^5$$

$$a_3 = g_2 + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u_2 dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1-2st)u_2 dt ds ds$$

$$a_3 = -\frac{559}{2520}s^2 + \frac{253}{4725}s^3 + \frac{7}{180}s^5 - \frac{17}{5400}s^6 - \frac{1}{10080}s^8 + \frac{1}{181440}s^9$$

$$u_3 = -\frac{559}{2520}t^2 + \frac{253}{4725}t^3 + \frac{7}{180}t^5 - \frac{17}{5400}t^6 - \frac{1}{10080}t^8 + \frac{1}{181440}t^9$$

$$a_4 = \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u_3 dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1-2st)u_3 dt ds ds$$

$$a_4 = -\frac{337}{453600}s^2 - \frac{811561}{74844000}s^3 - \frac{559}{151200}s^5 + \frac{253}{567000}s^6 + \frac{1}{8640}s^8 - \frac{17}{2721600}s^9$$

$$-\frac{1}{9979200}s^{11} + \frac{1}{239500800}s^{12}$$

$$u_4 = -\frac{337}{453600}t^2 - \frac{811561}{74844000}t^3 - \frac{559}{151200}t^5 + \frac{253}{567000}t^6 + \frac{1}{8640}t^8 - \frac{17}{2721600}t^9$$

$$-\frac{1}{9979200}t^{11} + \frac{1}{239500800}t^{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_5 &= \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u_4 dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1-2st)u_4 dt ds ds \\
 a_5 &= \frac{1}{8553600} s^{11} - \frac{17}{3592512000} s^{12} - \frac{1}{21794572800} s^{14} + \frac{1}{653837184000} s^{15} - \frac{559}{50803200} s^8 \\
 &+ \frac{253}{285768000} s^9 - \frac{811561}{8981280000} s^6 - \frac{33749}{27216000} s^5 - \frac{2694272117}{108972864000} s^2 + \frac{22964369}{12770257500} s^3 \\
 u_5 &= \frac{1}{8553600} t^{11} - \frac{17}{3592512000} t^{12} - \frac{1}{21794572800} t^{14} + \frac{1}{653837184000} t^{15} - \frac{559}{50803200} t^8 \\
 &+ \frac{253}{285768000} t^9 - \frac{811561}{8981280000} t^6 - \frac{33749}{27216000} t^5 - \frac{2694272117}{108972864000} t^2 + \frac{22964369}{12770257500} t^3 \\
 a_6 &= \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_0^s u_5 dt ds ds + \int_0^s \int_0^s \int_{-1}^1 (1-2st)u_5 dt ds ds \\
 a_6 &= \frac{1}{18681062400} s^{14} - \frac{17}{9807557760000} s^{15} - \frac{1}{88921857024000} s^{17} + \frac{1}{3201186852864000} s^{18} \\
 &- \frac{559}{50295168000} s^{11} + \frac{23}{3429216000} s^{12} - \frac{811561}{4526565120000} s^9 - \frac{33749}{9144576000} s^8 - \frac{2694272117}{6538371840000} s^5 \\
 &+ \frac{22964369}{1532430900000} s^6 - \frac{1035500137}{8506555200000} s^3 - \frac{481945007}{58378320000} s^2 \\
 u_6 &= \frac{1}{18681062400} t^{14} - \frac{17}{9807557760000} t^{15} - \frac{1}{88921857024000} t^{17} + \frac{1}{3201186852864000} t^{18} \\
 &- \frac{559}{50295168000} t^{11} + \frac{23}{3429216000} t^{12} - \frac{811561}{4526565120000} t^9 - \frac{33749}{9144576000} t^8 - \frac{2694272117}{6538371840000} t^5 \text{ then,} \\
 &+ \frac{22964369}{1532430900000} t^6 - \frac{1035500137}{8506555200000} t^3 - \frac{481945007}{58378320000} t^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$u_n(t) = u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + u_4 + u_5 + u_6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_n(t) &= 2 + 6t - \frac{445185020941}{148599360000} t^2 - \frac{27634519753}{416821204800000} t^3 + \frac{1349207323}{6538371840000} t^5 + \frac{514817}{111495200000} t^6 \\
 &+ \frac{16831}{9144576000} t^8 - \frac{130441}{4526565120000} t^9 + \frac{281}{50295168000} t^{11} + \frac{43}{377213760000} t^{12} + \frac{1}{130767436800} t^{14} \\
 &- \frac{1}{4903778880000} t^{15} - \frac{1}{88921857024000} t^{17} + \frac{1}{3201186852864000} t^{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

(16)

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_n(s) &= 2 + 6s - \frac{445185020941}{148599360000} s^2 - \frac{27634519753}{416821204800000} s^3 + \frac{1349207323}{6538371840000} s^5 + \frac{514817}{111495200000} s^6 \\
 &+ \frac{16831}{9144576000} s^8 - \frac{130441}{4526565120000} s^9 + \frac{281}{50295168000} s^{11} + \frac{43}{377213760000} s^{12} + \frac{1}{130767436800} s^{14} \\
 &- \frac{1}{4903778880000} s^{15} - \frac{1}{88921857024000} s^{17} + \frac{1}{3201186852864000} s^{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

(17)

Table of Results

The tables of numerical results below provide a structured presentation of data, allowing for easy interpretation and analysis.

Table 1: Numerical results for example 1

S	Exact	NMADM		Uwaheren <i>et. al.</i> (2022)	
		N=2	Error	N=5	Error
0	0	0	0	0.000000	0
0.1	0.100933	0.100933	1.3900 E-17	0.100933	3.0000 E-11
0.2	0.208269	0.208269	5.2700 E-16	0.208269	2.6000 E-09
0.3	0.330620	0.330620	4.4400 E-14	0.330620	4.3300 E-08
0.4	0.479018	0.479018	1.0500 E-12	0.479019	3.2430 E-07
0.5	0.666926	0.666926	1.2200 E-11	0.666927	1.5448 E-06
0.6	0.910242	0.910242	9.0700 E-11	0.900248	5.5266 E-06
0.7	1.227318	1.227318	4.9400 E-10	1.227334	1.6229 E-05
0.8	1.638956	1.638956	2.1400 E-09	1.638997	4.1242 E-05
0.9	2.168427	2.168427	7.8200 E-09	2.168521	9.3840 E-05
1	2.841471	2.841471	2.4900 E-08	2.841667	1.9568 E-04

Table 2: Numerical results for example 2

S	Exact	NMADM		Abubakar A. & Taiwo O. A. (2014)					
		N = 6	Error	Power Series		Chebyshev Polynomial		Legendre's Polynomial	
				N = 6	Error	N = 6	Error	N = 6	Error
0	2	2	0	2	0	2.00016	1.000 E-4	2.00251	2.510 E-3
0.1	2.57	2.57004	4.120 E-5	2.55934	1.066 E-3	2.57014	1.400 E-4	2.57113	1.130 E-3
0.2	3.08	3.08017	1.650 E-4	3.07856	1.440 E-3	3.08056	5.600 E-4	3.08164	1.640 E-3
0.3	3.53	3.53037	3.700 E-4	3.55621	2.621 E-4	3.53027	2.700 E-4	3.54712	1.712 E-3
0.4	3.92	3.92066	6.580 E-4	3.94830	2.830 E-3	3.91945	5.500 E-4	3.91867	1.400 E-3
0.5	4.25	4.25103	1.030 E-3	4.28391	3.391 E-3	4.24932	6.800 E-4	4.24801	1.990 E-3
0.6	4.52	4.52149	1.487 E-3	4.54167	2.167 E-3	4.51814	1.860 E-3	4.51772	2.280 E-3
0.7	4.73	4.73203	2.034 E-3	4.74893	1.893 E-3	4.73004	4.000 E-5	4.73105	1.050 E-3
0.8	4.88	4.88267	2.674 E-3	4.89642	1.642 E-3	4.88151	1.510 E-3	4.88240	2.400 E-3
0.9	4.97	4.97342	3.416 E-3	4.98341	1.341 E-3	4.97793	7.930 E-3	4.97806	8.060 E-3
1	5	5.00427	4.268 E-3	4.99672	3.280 E-3	4.99996	4.000 E-5	4.99507	1.930 E-3

Figures of Results

Introducing figures in results is crucial for conveying data visually which enhance comprehension and highlight key findings

Figure 1: Error comparison of NMADM & Akbari Ganji’s Method for Example 1

Figure 2: Error comparison of NMADM, Collocation by Power Series, Chebyshev Polynomial & Legendre’s Polynomial for Example 2

Discussion of Results

Table 1 (Numerical Results of Example 1) shows that the Akbari-Ganji technique has a maximum error of 1.9568 E-04 after the fifth iteration, whereas the new modified Adomian decomposition method (NMADM) has a maximum error of 2.49 E-08 after the second iteration at x = 1.0 for both methods.

Table 2 (Numerical Results of Example 2) shows that the NMADM outperforms the Power Series of 1.006 E-3 at x = 0.1, Chebyshev Polynomials of 1.510 E-3 at x = 0.8, Legendre's Polynomial of 1.130 E-3 at x = 0.1, and the NMADM of 1.030 E-3 at x = 0.5.

While Figure 1 illustrates an error comparison of NMADM and Akbari-Ganji's approach, figure 2 provides an error comparison of NMADM, Collocation by Power Series, Chebyshev Polynomials, and Legendre's Polynomial. As a result, the new modified Adomian decomposition method (NMADM) is said to outperform existing methods.

Conclusion

The conclusion of the novel modified Adomian decomposition approach for integro-differential equations implies that it is useful for solving such problems. The approach outperforms Akbari-Ganji's method and various polynomials in terms of convergence and accuracy, making it a viable tool for tackling mathematical issues involving integrals.

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